

BRIDGING THE DIVIDE: DEPOLARISING THE CONVERSATION ON SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

EVENT REPORT

Photo: Markus Spiske

This report reflects the outcomes and discussions of the workshop, "Bridging the Divide: Depolarising the Conversation on Sustainable Agriculture", which was co-organised by Re-Imagine Europa (RIE) and the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA), and held in Lisbon, Portugal on 31 January 2024.

WHY TACKLE POLARISED NARRATIVES IN SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE?

Developing sustainable food systems, which include the full spectrum of actors and their activities involved in the production, aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption and disposal of food products that originate from agriculture, forestry or fisheries and the broader natural and social environments in which they are embedded, is a complex issue.¹ There are several interconnected dimensions and objectives to consider: feeding a growing population, ensuring food safety and security, promoting environmental sustainability, safeguarding rural communities' culture and way of life, and enabling technological innovation and economic progress. These goals, while essential, can sometimes appear to be in conflict with one another. Building sustainable food systems in Europe (and indeed globally) is an existential challenge – one that is made harder to overcome when conversations around potential solutions and policy reforms devolve into false dichotomies, such as “us versus them” or “right versus wrong” narratives. Diverse perspectives and good-faith dissent are essential to democratic societies, but diversity should not be mistaken for polarisation. To address polarisation effectively, we need innovative approaches that go beyond the traditional ‘information deficit model’.²

The increasingly polarised nature of the debates around food and food systems, particularly agricultural systems, has been well documented, and is playing out on the streets, in policy circles, and the media. The recent and ongoing farmer protests across Europe, the EU's roll-back of environmentally friendly regulations on emission targets and pesticide-use, and the ongoing public demonstrations by climate activists are some highly visible expressions of the polarised discourse. These debates are also taking place within a wider context of rampant mis- and disinformation, which are increasingly being highlighted as risks to human development and societal cohesion and progress.

Recognising that the path to a sustainable food system involves not just technological innovation, but also a change in the way conversations take place on the ground, i.e., less polarisation and more consensus-building around shared values, Re-Imagine Europa (RIE) and the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA) jointly developed an interdisciplinary workshop, held in Lisbon, Portugal, on 31st January 2024, that brought together leading voices in the subject matter of agriculture and plant breeding (including the subject of new genomic techniques – NGTs), as well as experts in the different facets of depolarisation/polarisation, including ‘trust in science’, science mis- and disinformation, science communication, citizen engagement, and science advice for evidence-based policymaking. The goal was to engage multidisciplinary and ideologically diverse stakeholders from the natural and social sciences, as well as policymakers, industry leaders, and civil society organisations, to explore and debate the latest research and insights on effective communication strategies that could be applied to the ‘hot’ topic of sustainable agriculture and the role of NGTs.

¹ FAO. (2018). Sustainable Food Systems: Concept and framework. *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. Available from: <https://www.fao.org/3/ca2079en/CA2079EN.pdf>.

² Grant, W. J. (2023). The knowledge deficit model and science communication. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Communication*. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228613.013.1396>.

THE PRIMARY OBJECTIVES OF THE WORKSHOP

1. To discuss effective (digital) communication, policy, and public engagement strategies for depolarising the debate on sustainable agriculture, particularly the highly-contested role of new genomic techniques (NGTs) in this conversation
2. To bring depolarisation methodologies from theory to praxis by immersing participants in a TableTop exercise that requires them to apply a structured, seven-point system to debate policy recommendations for a simulated crisis scenario
3. To engage diverse stakeholders, across disciplines, sectors, and ideological perspectives, in examining the various and interconnected dimensions of depolarising the debate on sustainable agriculture

METHODOLOGY: HOW DO WE DEPOLARISE?

The workshop took a two-pronged approach to the “problem” of *‘depolarising the conversation on sustainable agriculture’*.

Prong 1: Expert Presentations (with Interactive Q&A)

ALLEA and RIE invited keynote speakers from both the natural and social sciences to share their insights into several key topics: the current state of the debate on NGTs and sustainable agriculture; the evolving role of social media in the interaction between the public and scientific expertise; effective strategies for science communication and citizen engagement; and the moral dimensions of public policy. The keynotes addressed both the technical aspects of sustainable agriculture, as well as the broader societal aspects – as they relate to the media, the public, and policymaking.

Urs Niggli, President of the Institute for Agroecology (agroecology.science), opened the workshop with an overview of modern breeding methods, as well as the current issues and controversies in the field of sustainable agriculture, emphasising the perceived conflict between technological innovations such as NGTs and environmental sustainability and biodiversity goals.

Prof Niggli’s presentation was followed by Donya Alinejad, Assistant Professor at Utrecht University and investigator of the [PERITIA](#) project, who shared her ongoing research on the growing (and often deleterious) impact of social media on public trust in science, experts, and expertise.

Barbara Gallani, Head of Communication and Partnerships (ENGAGE) at the European Food Safety Authority ([EFSA](#)), then took the stage to share EFSA’s insights into the conversations taking place among the European public on the interconnected issues of health, food safety, NGTs, and climate change.

This was followed by Mario Scharfbillig, Science Policy Advisor at the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre ([JRC](#)), who delved into strategies of effective science communication, which need to go beyond the ‘information deficit model’, by considering factors such as values, identities, media formats, and social trust. You can read more about the JRC report on the significance of values and identities to policymaking and politics [here](#).

To close the first half of the workshop, Andrzej Nowak, Chief Narrative Scientist at RIE, and Marcin Napiórkowski, Contemporary Mythologies Scholar, who recently co-authored RIE’s [‘Depolarisation Manual’](#), presented their ideas on how to avoid political stalemates, depolarise highly fractious debates (such as the one around NGTs in agriculture), and foster more inclusive dialogue, utilising their seven-step [R.E.F.R.A.M.E Methodology](#) (hereafter, “REFRAME”).

The presentations set the stage for an interdisciplinary approach to the conversations on NGTs and sustainable agriculture, moving beyond addressing technology-related questions to debating issues of trust in science, public engagement, and socio-cultural values, which are demonstrably important variables impacting the current debate in Europe. There was a robust Q&A component, during which participants addressed such questions as *“How do we deal with bad faith actors?”*, *“Can we regulate social media platforms to improve science communications?”*, *“How do we communicate under conditions of uncertainty and evolving scientific evidence?”*, among others. The Q&A

discussions demonstrated the significance of taking an interdisciplinary, intersectoral, and inclusive approach to debating seemingly niche topics such as NGTs and sustainable agriculture. The presentations were livestreamed and can be viewed [here](#). You can also find key highlights from the speakers' keynotes [here](#) and [here](#).

Prong 2: TableTop Exercise

ALLEA and RIE jointly designed a TableTop exercise that immersed participants in a [crisis simulation](#) and required them to play pre-designed [roles](#) to discuss a (fictitious) contentious topic in a constructive way. The participants were divided into three groups and required to apply RIE's REFRAME Methodology to conduct their discussions. This seven-point systematic approach to discourse around highly emotional and polarising topics was developed to help stakeholders across the ideological spectrum navigate much needed debates on the relevant subject with respect, empathy, and efficiency. Prior to the workshop, participants received the details of REFRAME, the crisis scenario, which involved debating whether to allow/ban a new fictional technology (named "Quantum Bioengineering, aka QBE") into the farming system, as well as their assigned roles. They were also provided with additional information on the "[pros](#)" and "[cons](#)" of QBE to bolster their arguments/discussions; they therefore had time to prepare their statements and narratives to engage in the role-playing exercise in a substantive way. It should be noted that the participants were encouraged to play roles in the simulation that differed from their everyday positions because such role-play potentially enables empathy and perspective-taking.³ Participants in the three groups were guided by their respective facilitators to apply the seven steps of REFRAME to their discussions on how to regulate the use of QBE. Andrzej Nowak and Marcin Napiórkowski, the creators of REFRAME, as well as Peter Kearns, Director of Sustainable Food Systems and Innovation at RIE, served as 'facilitators'. The goal of the exercise was two-fold:

1. **Primary aim:** To apply the REFRAME Methodology in practice in order to test its viability as a depolarisation tool
2. **Secondary aim:** To identify potential (policy) recommendations on how to integrate NGTs into the sustainability toolbox in food production

Both the simulated scenario, as well as the "points of contention and controversy" around QBE, were modelled on the current questions and debates surrounding the use of NGTs in Europe.

Main Takeaways

The TableTop exercise, involving the application of REFRAME to a simulated crisis, saw most participants engage enthusiastically with their roles to debate the issues. Given that the primary aim of the TableTop exercise was to evaluate the viability of REFRAME as a depolarisation tool, the following report will mainly be limited to participants' feedback on their experience of using the tool within the context of the simulation, rather than a recounting of the specifics of the debates and arguments put forth by the participants.

Several arguments made by participants in favour of/against the fictional technology QBE mirrored the ongoing debates on NGTs. For example, participants identified that there was tension between

³"Perspective-taking is a complex and multifaceted sociocognitive process that enables us to recognise and appreciate another person's point-of-view, whether it be the same or different from our own. Previous work has shown that perspective-taking is closely related to and a key aspect of human empathy, which refers to the ability to internally simulate and adopt the mental states of others. Perhaps unsurprisingly then, both perspective-taking and empathy are critical in guiding successful social interactions, effective communication, and prosocial behaviour." Healey, M. L., & Grossman, M. (2018). Cognitive and affective perspective-taking: Evidence for shared and dissociable anatomical substrates. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2018.00491>

deliberative democracy and evidence-based policy, and considered questions such as “*Is it worthwhile to have conversations with science denialists?*”, “*Should some scientific issues be beyond the purview of the voting public?*”. This is a positive demonstration of the value in developing fictional scenarios to discuss contentious topics because they show that such scenarios facilitate the generation and exchange of ideas that are directly applicable to real-world challenges. By creating a certain distance from entrenched beliefs and resolved stances, such simulation exercises allow participants to engage in more open and respectful conversations. This approach further nurtures diverse perspectives that could contribute meaningfully to discussions, ultimately fostering constructive dialogue and progress on complex issues.

While several participants engaged substantively in the exercise, some did allude to a lack of preparation time. This issue is expected to recur occasionally in future iterations, given the demands of participants’ schedules and competing priorities. Those who felt satisfied with their assigned roles tended to invest more effort in preparing for the simulation. Interestingly, some found it easier to take on perspectives vastly different from their own, while others preferred role-playing their actual positions. Some participants added that as some participants did not take a role different from their usual perspective, this resulted in an imbalance of argumentative power. Given this feedback on the significance of the ‘role’ to engaging with the exercise, but the differing preferences, the organisers have identified that a possible ‘solution’ to improve the next iteration would be to make role-assignment random.

It was also noted that there needed to be more ideological diversity. Participants suggested that perhaps consensus-building during the exercise was relatively easy as compared to the real world because those present had a high degree of agreement with each other, and some stakeholders (such as NGOs and farmers) were under-represented. It would be useful to conduct the next iteration with a more heterogeneous group of stakeholders on the ideological as well as sectoral spectrum, especially with practitioners engaged in the farming sector.

Some participants further noted that it was important to consider the fact that the people “in the room” of the discussion are not those driving the polarisation of the debate(s). They suggested that even if REFRAME works in depolarising the debate among the participants, civil society organisations and NGOs often represent the interests of their funders who are rarely in the room and feedback to them is limited. More work is needed to find a way to engage these delegated debate forms and scale such engagement efforts beyond direct participation.

Participants suggested that the exercise could be simplified, gamified (through the introduction of scoring and cooperation/competition), and made more scientifically rigorous. For instance, they recommended adding a ‘pre- and post-survey’ on attitudes to, and knowledge of, the subject of polarisation. This is being explored by the organisers for possible future iterations.

NEXT STEPS

Given the positive feedback on the workshop in Lisbon, RIE and ALLEA are jointly organising an online workshop series, scheduled for the second half of 2024 to address the various facets of polarised narratives in the field of sustainable food systems, both at the level of individual agents and systemic structures, as well as to further explore methods, approaches, and practical tools to depolarise debates.

To ensure an interdisciplinary and intersectoral approach to this complex subject, ALLEA and RIE have convened a Strategic Advisory Group to hone the content of the workshop series so that different approaches to assess and tackle 'depolarisation' can be examined, discussed, and, ultimately, deployed. The group comprises expert representatives of international governmental and non-governmental organisations (e.g., [FAO](#), [EFSA](#), [IPES-Food](#), [JRC](#)), European Academies and their networks (e.g., [SAPEA](#), [The Royal Society](#), [RACAB](#)), and social and natural scientists working on sustainable agriculture and/or depolarisation (e.g., from research projects such as [PERITIA](#), [SCI-BORG](#)).

The question of how to make our food systems more efficient and sustainable without sacrificing biodiversity or compromising food and economic security is complex, highly emotional, and, currently, extremely polarising. It is imperative that the debates on how to arrive at viable solutions are constructive, respectful, and fruitful. Depolarising these debates with a diversity of tools adapted to different contexts, particularly against the backdrop of increasingly contentious geopolitical realities, is therefore of paramount importance for effective science communications and evidence-based policymaking, and ultimately, for shaping the strategic and economic future of Europe.

ALLEA and Re-Imagine Europa would like to thank our participants for their spirited and robust engagement with the themes and exercises of the workshop.

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ABOUT ALLEA

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing more than 50 academies from about 40 countries in Europe. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines. Learn more here: www.allea.org

ABOUT RE-IMAGINE EUROPA

Re-Imagine Europa (RIE) is a nonpartisan think tank that delivers world-class interdisciplinary and intersectoral research to address some of the most challenging issues we face as a society. Founded by President Giscard d'Estaing to honour his friendship with Chancellor Helmut Schmidt, the organisation works with an innovative methodology based on narratives to look for shared values and solutions that go beyond personal, national or political interests. Following the successful implementation of the innovative narrative methodology, in 2023 Re-Imagine Europa launched the first Narratives Observatory to combat disinformation and polarisation in Europe Systemically (NODES), as a pilot project financed by the European Commission and set up by seven research and media partners from across four EU countries – Belgium, France, Poland, Italy.

ABOUT RIE'S TASKFORCE ON SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS AND INNOVATION

The RIE Task Force on Sustainable Food Systems and Innovation was created as a forum that facilitates constructive dialogue among a wide range of stakeholders with different viewpoints, with the primary goal of going beyond political stalemates and finding new, shared pathways forward. Working with the innovative Narrative Methodology, the Task Force focuses on very specific challenges to contribute to the global challenge of building a robust and resilient food system and becoming a global standard for sustainability while protecting biodiversity and reducing land use. Within the Task Force on Sustainable Food Systems and Innovation RIE has engaged Strategic and Knowledge Partners (incl. Allea) as well as a network of over 100 Experts.

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